

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SELF-PACED LEARNING TO
THE JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF MARY
IMMACULATE PARISH SPECIAL SCHOOL**

A Research Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements in Inquiries, Investigations, & Immersion
for Grade 12 – Senior High School

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In partial fulfillment of the Requirements Inquiries, Investigation, and Immersion in Senior High School, this Paper entitled "The Effectiveness of Self-Paced Learning to the Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School," has been prepared and submitted by Juliana Lynelle B. Tribunal, John Loyd A. Carnasa, Pauleen Ann N. Dingcong, Kirsten Ashley M. Magpantay, Ramelle John M. Trasporto, and Allysson O. Tumangday, who are hereby recommended for oral examination.

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ABSTRACT

During the COVID-19 pandemic, people have experienced a lot of difficulties. Different economic sectors struggled to adjust quickly to the so-called “new normal.” In terms of education, a lot have struggled to adjust personally because not everyone has the capability to afford the necessities and resources to conduct online classes. In response to the sudden change in the educational system, the Department of Education implemented the “Online Distance Learning,” also known as ODL, that allows students to continue their studies with and without the use of gadgets such as laptops, phones, etc. However, there were still difficulties encountered because students only rely on the modules distributed. Despite the struggles that is present in modular learning, students may develop their skills and abilities especially in critical thinking, problem solving, metamemory and metacomprehension. This study provides a review of scholarly sources for determining the efficacy of Self-Paced Learning on the students who choose the modular learning modality. The findings of the study indicate that Self-Paced learning helps students to be critically minded, cognitive, flexible, and improve processing speed. In this case students need to be productive to be able to do and finish the modules on time.

Keywords: *Self-Paced Learning, abilities, students, critically minded*

Table of Contents

	Pages
Chapter 1 - The Problem and Its Background	
1.1 Introduction.....	9
1.2 Significance of the Study	11
1.3 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework	12
1.4 Statement of the Problem	13
1.5 Hypothesis	14
1.6 Definition of Terms	14
1.7 Scope and Delimitation of the Study.....	15
Chapter 2 - Review of Related Literature and Studies	
2.1 Self-paced/Modular Learning.....	16
2.2 Advantages of Modular and Self-Paced Learning.....	18
2.3 Disadvantages of Modular and Self-Paced Learning.....	21
2.4 Challenges in Modular and Self-Paced Learning.....	25
Chapter 3 - Methodology of the Study	
3.1 Methods and Techniques of the Study	28
3.2 Locale of the Study	28

3.3 Population and Sample of the study	29
3.4 Instrument of the Study.....	29
3.5 Method of Data Collection.....	30
3.6 Statistical Treatment	31

Chapter 4 - Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Personal Information (Demographics).....	33
Table 2.....	33
4.2 Advantages of Modular & Self-Paced Learning.....	34-40
Table 3.....	34
Table 4.....	35
Table 5.....	36
Table 6.....	37
Table 7.....	37
Table 8.....	38
Table 9.....	39
Table 10.....	40
4.3 Disadvantages of Modular & Self-Paced Learning.....	41-49
Table 11.....	41
Table 12.....	42
Table 13.....	43

Table 14.....	44
Table 15.....	45
Table 16.....	46
Table 17.....	47
Table 18.....	48
Table 19.....	49
4.4 Challenges in Modular & Self-Paced Learning.....	50-55
Table 20.....	50
Table 21.....	51
Table 22.....	52
Table 23.....	53
Table 24.....	54
Table 25.....	55
Table 26.....	55
4.5 Possible Solutions to ensure Quality Education through Modular & Self-Paced Learning.....	56-64
Table 27.....	56
Table 28.....	57
Table 29.....	58
Table 30.....	59

Table 31.....	60
Table 32.....	61
Table 33.....	62
Table 34.....	63
Table 35.....	64

Chapter 5: Summary, Conclusions, and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of Findings.....	65-70
5.2 Conclusions.....	70-72
5.3 Recommendations.....	72-74
5.4 References.....	75-77

List of Tables

Respondents of the Study.....	29
-------------------------------	----

List of Figures

Conceptual model of the Study.....	13
------------------------------------	----

List of Appendices

Communication Letters.....	78-79
Instrument of the Study.....	80-81
Curriculum Vitae.....	82-87

CHAPTER I

Problem and Its Background

INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 Pandemic has made a huge impact on every nation's education system all around the globe. From learning face-to-face in a classroom setup, schools have already switched to acquiring new knowledge and adapted new teaching styles through the use of modern technologies via video conferencing software or tools such as Zoom, MS Teams, and Google Meet because of strict quarantine measures. Last August 2020, Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones (2020) stated in her previous press, briefing that education should not come to an end just because of the unnecessary events that happened. In response to the situation, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented a new educational system known as "Online Distance Learning," which will enable students to study at their own pace and to prevent having face-to-face interactions at the same time.

Moreover, this new educational system consists of three different modalities that the Department of Education offers, namely: Full Online, Semi-Online (Blended Learning), and Modular. In both face-to-face and online classes, teachers and students have real-time interaction. The key element in full online is the use of the internet. Online learning refers to the idea of using online platforms for learning (Pop A. 2021). Lectures, assignments, and exams are all conducted using virtual platforms. Next, Blended Learning, also known as "Semi-Online," is a combination of learning at a distance and traditional learning. Learners have a (more or less) fixed schedule where they have to attend a part of the classes. However, most activities would be done online (Pop A. 2021). Lastly in the Modular Learning, according to Manlangit P., et al. (2020), modular

learning is a form of distance learning that uses Self-Learning Modules that are based on the most essential learning competencies provided by the Department of Education.

Meanwhile, both students and instructors have a hard time adjusting to the new normal in the education system, as they were used to the typical classroom set-up. Inside the classroom, students are not only able to participate, but they also get to address their concerns directly to the teacher. As a matter of fact, students were in an environment wherein they are less prone to distractions. Unlike now, a lot of learners have experienced numerous interruptions which makes their learning difficult and challenging. According to The Manila Times, thousands of public school teachers and administrators had a near-rebellion against DepEd. This suggests that there are shortcomings of the distance learning system, as there are much graver problems than just some minor content errors.

Furthermore, aside from the challenges that they experience throughout the school year, some students are having a hard time to comprehend lessons, especially those who are in the Modular Learning Modality that conduct self-paced study. On the other hand, Manlangit, et al. (2020) strongly spelled out that even though most Filipino parents are literate enough to teach their children, still, not all of them are qualified to teach. In connection to this, Madarang (2020) pointed out that a lot of students and parents are concerned about the errors in the modules which varies in spelling, grammar, equations and directions. Hence, the quality, relativity as well as the accuracy of the given modules have a major impact on the effectiveness of self-paced learning. Because of this, the independent variables of this study are the challenges, advantages and disadvantages. The dependent variable the effectiveness of modular and self-paced learning.

In Mary Immaculate Parish Special School (MIPSS), the researchers seek to find solutions for the purpose of improving the quality of self-paced learning to students. Hence, this study was conducted to know and to evaluate the effectiveness of self-paced during the new normal,

specifically to the students from the Junior High School Department who are currently enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of self-paced learning to the Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School (MIPSS), specifically those students from Grade 7 to Grade 10. Through knowing these, the researchers should be able to conclude the strengths and weaknesses of the modular modality and its benefits.

The findings of the study shall benefit the following:

Learners

The learners or students from MIPSS would benefit from this study through knowing their weak points regarding the school subjects and topics that they acquire through modular (self-paced) learning. They would also know what are the most effective solutions they need to do in order to address their concerns and questions and to have efficient and effective communication with their teachers.

Teachers

The teachers from Mary Immaculate Parish Special School would know how to properly and effectively deliver their lessons through the use of modules, prepare their lesson plans, and would know the challenges met and perspective of their students. The teachers will also know what measures to take whenever both him/her and the students would encounter in the distributed modules.

Parents

The parents of students would also benefit from this study in a way that they would know how to help their child/children in their studies. They would also know the difficulties that their

child would possibly encounter, monitor their studies, and they could also be a helpful contact between the student and teacher.

School Administration

The School Administration of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School would determine what is lacking in their own educational system, address the concerns of their staff and students, and develop different and flexible strategies to deliver quality education despite the new normal. It would also encourage them to monitor and proof-read the modules prepared by the respective teachers before printing and distribution.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study is anchored on **Bruner's Constructivist Theory**. It supports the idea that learners can build their understanding by exploring on their own or self-paced especially if given important, correct and relevant tools are used.

Furthermore, this theory which was constructed by Jerome Seymour Bruner, one of the first proponents of constructivism which is an epistemological belief about what "knowing" is and how one "comes to know", the aim of learning is not to enlighten people, but rather to encourage the reasoning and problem-solving skills of children that can then be translated to a variety of circumstances. Bruner (1961) suggests that learners acquire knowledge and to do this using a coding system to organize and categorize information. Instead of being told by the instructor, Bruner believed that the most efficient way to establish a coding system is to explore it. The philosophy of constructivism by Bruner encompasses the principle of learning as an active method in which learners may create fresh concepts depending about what their present knowledge is and also their prior experience. The tools used by the instructor should concentrate on promoting, assisting and enabling the child to explore the core concepts out of their own. The main principle is good communication and contact between the students and the teachers.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1

Figure 1 shown above presents the conceptual framework of the study. It is composed of two variables. The advantages, disadvantages as well as challenges met by the students as an independent variable and effectiveness of modular and Self-paced learning to the Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School as the dependent variable.

The independent variables pertain to the problems or difficulties that a certain student experience, specifically those who are in modular mode of learning or self-paced learning. Some challenges may include problems within the environment, modules and the like. On the other hand, the effectiveness of modular and self-paced modules as the dependent variable pertains to how effective these materials are.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The major concern of the study is to assess the effectiveness of self-paced learning during the new normal to the Junior High School students of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School (MIPSS) who are enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality.

Specifically, this study ought to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What are the advantages of modular and self-paced learning?
2. What are the disadvantages of modular and self-paced learning?
3. What challenges were met by the students conducting modular and self-paced learning?
4. What are the possible solutions to ensure quality education to students given the challenges experienced?

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The researchers have hypothesized that the advantages, disadvantages and challenges have an impact on the effectiveness of self-paced learning through modules. Thus, the researchers assumed that the self-paced learning of Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Special School is effective.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

1. **Effectiveness** - The degree to which something is successful in producing a desired result; success
2. **Evaluation** - the process of judging or calculating the quality, importance, amount, or value of something:
3. **Modular Learning** - an approach to education that uses modules based on the most essential learning competencies provided by the Department of Education.
4. **Self-Paced Learning** - is defined as a specific learning method in which the learner is able to control the amount of material they consume as well as the duration of time they need to learn the new information properly.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

This research is only limited to sixty-eight (68) students of the Junior High School in Mary Immaculate Parish Special School, specifically who chose the Modular Learning Modality. It highlights the advantages, disadvantages and challenges of Self-Paced Learning.

CHAPTER II

Review of Related Literature

SELF-PACED/MODULAR LEARNING

Perez A. (2020), *Weighing Modular Learning*. As mentioned by Perez, A. (2020), modular learning is the most preferred mode of learning in rural areas in the country because online education is not feasible and aside from not having access from the internet, students do not have gadgets to use as stated by Osman L. Paidan. In addition, the implementation of modular learning is not going well for some provinces in the Philippines specifically in Manay town as 20 out of 68 students lack the ability to read, write and comprehend by themselves. Furthermore, Paidan pointed out that some parents are illiterate and they are not too capable of reading with comprehension which makes the whole situation complicated. Fortunately, the Manay North District came up with a plan to help the parents as well as their children by implementing a Reading Remediation Program that will allow teachers and students to have a face-to-face learning system to enable them to read and comprehend before the classes resume.

Sejpal K. (2013), *Modular Method of Teaching*. As stated in a study conducted by Sejpal K. (2013), the primary objective of distance learning is to resolve location and time barriers. One of the most significant aims of distance learning is to give learners who are not physically present at school an opportunity for education, frequently on an individual basis. The goal of distance learning is to ensure a good relationship between students and instructors. That's why distance learning often has drawbacks as well as benefits. It takes into account the differences of a person between the learners who need to prepare and follow the most effective teaching strategies to help the person grow and mature at his or her own rate.

Some of the advantages include students may have the convenience of having the course materials sent to their homes, students can learn useful skills that can be transferred, such as planning and research, also in terms of travel, learning has become more effective, it establishes an evaluation scheme other than marks or ratings. In their own working area, users study the modules. Without upsetting the regular duties and obligations, users may research. For single use, small group or large group modules may be administered. Modules are modular such that a number of patterns can be used for implementation. It helps the student to be in charge of his learning and accept greater learning accountability. In the new educational situation, it has already reached broader accessibility.

As for the disadvantages, for undisciplined learners or inflexible teachers, distance learning is not sufficient, in their use, modules are economical and it is suitable for mature students only. These techniques require smart classrooms. In terms of education, students need to be more involved but it is not possible to offer laboratory and experimental courses remotely.

Lapada A. et al. (2020), *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research* 19 (6), 127-144, 2020: Teachers' Covid-19 Awareness, Distance Learning Education Experiences and Perceptions towards Institutional Readiness and Challenges. According to Lapada A. et al. 2020, this study explored and tackled the teachers' awareness about the COVID-19 pandemic and their opinions on their respective schools' readiness, as well as their response to the challenges of conducting effective distance learning education in the country. The data gathering procedure was done through Google forms, which, after validation from the respective DepEd divisions and universities, were subsequently sent to the teachers via email. In contrast, teachers' gender, length of teaching experience, and geographic location have significant differences with their readiness to distance learning education.

Manlangit P., et al. (2020), *Filipino Students Prefer Modular Learning.* According to this article by Manlangit P., et al. (2020), this study talks about Self-Learning Modules (SLM)

based on the most essential learning competencies (MELCS) provided by DepEd. Based on data gathered via DepEd's National Learner Enrolment and Survey Forms (LESFs), as 8.8 million out of the 22.2 million enrollees (39.6% of total respondents) preferred modular distance learning for the upcoming school year. It is mentioned that a public secondary school in San Carlos City, Pangasinan, modular learning also emerged as the most preferred learning mode.

Bernardo, J. (2020), *Modular Learning most preferred parents: DepEd.* According to Bernardo (2020), learning through printed and digital modules were the most preferred distance learning method of parents who enrolled their children in the coming school year, based on a survey conducted by the Department of Education (DepEd).

During the 45-day enrollment period in public schools that ended July 15, 2020, parents and guardians were made to answer the DepEd's Learner Enrollment and Survey Form. It asked them about their preferred alternative learning mode, and sought to profile the enrollee's readiness for distance education.

Survey results released Thursday by the DepEd showed that 8.9 million parents preferred modular distance learning, where students at home would study through self-learning modules.

ADVANTAGES OF MODULAR AND SELF-PACED LEARNING

Bautista, R.G., (2015), *Optimizing Classroom Instruction through Self-Paced Learning Prototype.* As claimed by the study, the researcher investigated the learning impact of the self-paced learning prototype in optimizing classroom instruction towards students' learning in Chemistry. Two sections of 64 Laboratory High School students in General High School Chemistry were used as subjects of the study. The Quasi-Experimental and Correlational Research Design was used in the study: a pre-test was conducted, scored and analyzed which served as the basis in determining the initial learning schema of the respondents. A questionnaire was adopted to find the learning motivation of the students in science. Using Pearson-r correlation, it was found out that

there is a highly significant relationship between their internal drive and their academic performance. Moreover, a post-test was conducted after a self-paced learning prototype was used in the development of select topics in their curriculum plot. It was found out that the students who experienced the self-paced learning prototype performed better in their academic performance as evidenced by the difference of their mean post-test results. Despite the lack of interaction, results are: students exposed to the self-paced learning prototype performed better in the subject as indicated by their post-test results; great impact of the self-paced learning prototype was observed among high ability students; however, marginal impact was observed among low ability students; the learner-respondents manifest a positive motivation in learning the subject. In general, it is concluded that a self-paced learning prototype optimizes students' performances and a potent tool in optimizing classroom instruction.

Chua E. & Monteagudo N. (2020), *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, Vol. 2, No. 3, Self – Paced Modules: Using Summarized Strategy in Science 8 Earth and Space for Students at Risk of Dropping Out (SARDO)*. According to Chua, et al. (2020), a large number of Filipino students were not given a chance to attend and finish formal basic education due to various reasons and barriers. Some have dropped out and became one of the out-of-school youth, while some do not have schools to go to in their neighborhood. Fortunately, the Department of Education found an alternative to help learners stated above by introducing the Modular Approach to teaching, where printed and/or soft-copy modules are prepared by teachers for the students. This study was then conducted to find out the efficacy of self-paced learning modules. The tests for dependent samples were utilized to determine the possible differences to the pre-assessment and post-assessment test scores of the students using the design paced module in Earth and Space. As a result, the researchers discovered that there was a significant dissimilarity in the pre-test and post-test of the students using the self-paced module as to their lower and high

order thinking skills. And this concludes that the use of a self-paced module is efficient in increasing the academic performance of the students.

Tullis J. & Benjamin A. (2011), *On the Effectiveness of Self-Paced Learning*. According to Tullis J. and Benjamin A., one of the major parts of self-paced learning is concluding how to assign study time. Students typically give more opportunities to things they judge to be troublesome, in any event when no time constraints exist. Giving students authority over investigation permits predispositions and errors in metacognitive observing to impact execution contrarily by driving students to settle on imperfect or counterproductive choices while controlling their examination. By investing more energy in these things, self-pacing subjects will fundamentally dedicate a more modest extent of time to the simple and medium-trouble things, and this decision could adversely affect general performance. In both experiments in this study, acknowledgment implementation for students who controlled their own personal study time was contrasted with students who spent a similar measure of general study time however saw the things for a standard measure of time. Students with control of study-time distribution altogether beat subjects with no control, in any event, when the complete investigation time was compared between groups. In this study, just inconsistency reducers outflanked their burdened accomplices, and error reducers made up not exactly 50% of all the self-managed subjects tried. Notwithstanding the methodology used during learning, other individual contrasts exist in the viability of executing control. (Dunsloky & Connor). Without absolute monitoring, suitable decisions cannot be made nor executed. In this research, not exactly 50% of all subjects executed a successful examination methodology. In conclusion, enhancements in metacognition could bring about more fruitful and effective learning, both through modular and/or online classes.

DISADVANTAGES OF MODULAR AND SELF-PACED LEARNING

Bernardo J. (2021), *Majority of Teachers Doubt if Distance Learning is Effective.* As reported from the Philippine's media conglomerate, Bernardo J. (2021) stated that the majority of Filipino teachers doubted the efficiency of the distance education setup. This is according to a nationwide online survey conducted by experts from the month of November in 2021, using the *Movement for Safe, Equitable, Quality, and Relevant Education (SEQuRe Education Movement)*. The learning competencies refer to a student's ability to demonstrate excellence in every learning activity, however, findings on the survey show a fractional quantity of students found errors in the modules that they use. Another result varies from students under the modular distance learning felt the absence of communication through the use of messenger and only four out of fifty-four students have kept pace with the lessons. Half of the respondents corresponded with the negative impacts on their physical and mental health in regards to distance-learning activities. As a result, the Department of Education implemented an "academic ease" policy to alleviate the stress felt by students, parents, and teachers in distance learning.

Clea (2021), *Students' New Normal: Modular Distance Learning.* According to this article, five disadvantages exist in the implementation of modular modality. The following disadvantages are: (1) Not all students do their modules whole-heartedly; students do their modules for formality purposes. (2) Some parents spoil their children and do the deed instead of their own; many parents spoil their children by doing the modules all by themselves and those who are privileged hire tutors for their children to answer their modules. (3) Some students tend to copy their answers from others without reading the module; they make group chats to pass the answers from one another. (4) Many students claimed that they actually never learn from the modules; they have difficulties in absorbing the information given. (5) Modules are for formality and not internalized by the students; the information given is not absorbed but rather focuses on the

requirement to finish the tasks. Given these disadvantages, it is difficult to attain the true form of learning as other students lack the motivation to be independent of their academics given the privilege of quality education. The existing disadvantage where information is not absorbed thoroughly shows the need of a guide where morality exists rather than of immoral guidance in a case where students are prone to cheating. The lack of information due to cheating will lead to graving difficulties as one steps ahead to another level. Moreover, the learning modality of students should not be of hindrance for their acquiring of knowledge as this will be used for future purposes.

Cheng, C. & Abu Bakar, M. (2017), *The Impact of Using Modules in the Teaching and Learning of English in Malaysian Polytechnics: An Analysis of the Views and Perceptions of English Language Teaching*. According to Cheng and Bakar, this study is pointed toward investigating instructors' perspectives and discernments on the effect of utilizing modules in the educating and learning of English in Malaysian Polytechnics. In this study, in accordance with the disadvantages of utilizing modules, most of the respondents felt that a portion of the teachers winds up being excessively dependent on the modules. Additionally, some likewise said understudies may turn out to be excessively subject to the module and consider it to be the main wellspring of data while others felt that the material in the module may demonstrate unacceptable to the requirements of their understudies and subsequently make exercises exhausting and insignificant. Also, almost half of them said the dependence on modules restricts the inventiveness of speakers while about half felt that the substance and materials in the module are outdated, or of an improper level to the understudies from the different projects.

Nonetheless, guarantee that it doesn't result in being situated corresponding to Communicative English. The respondents collectively concur that there are the two preferences just as hindrances to utilizing the module. Presently, the entirety of the respondents utilize the module, yet the recurrence and reason fluctuate starting with one individual then onto the next.

Inkson, D. & Smith, E. (2001), *Self-Paced Learning: A Student's Perspective.*

According to this study by Inkson & Smith (2001), a small scale of study was conducted at TAFE NSW College where five groups of students were addressed to seek volunteers for the research. Self-paced learning seems to develop several positive characteristics, such as self-reliance and independence, in some students (Watson, 1991a, p 18). It seems clear, however, from the literature, that SPL does not suit all groups of students. The students from Non English Speaking Backgrounds (NESB), older adults, young people, long-term unemployed, and those with literacy problems seem to have difficulty with self-paced learning (Smith et al, 1997, p 63-64; James, 2000; Misko, 2000; Choy & Delahaye, 2000). Boote (1998) notes that students with disabilities need particular support, although with such support they can succeed with self-paced learning. Four participants who met the required criteria from a non-English speaking background and without regular access to computers were recruited as case study subjects. Although the students liked the arrangements associated with self-paced learning it appears equally that they were not particularly well served in teaching and learning terms by self-paced learning as it was practiced in the Learning Centre, and judging from the literature, in many other VET providers. The two major issues were the inability of teachers to give adequate individual attention, and the lack of suitable preparation courses for students entering self-paced learning for the first time. This is to place the awareness in the disadvantage of self-paced learning as stated above whereas the teachers lacked the ability to provide individual attention and preparation in handling students. As a result, students came across with difficulties in focusing on their assigned tasks.

Jiang, L., et al. (2015), *Self-Paced Curriculum Learning.* According to this study, the novel regime, which is self-paced curriculum learning, implemented an algorithm to distinguish the divergence of curriculum-learning and self-paced learning. Results showed that a specific type of set is required that follows distribution of the test set in some problems. The set is comparable to the mock exam in education whose purposes are to let students realize how well they would

perform on the real test to have a better idea of what to study. Different learning schemes were conducted to solve the challenges of diversity in learning whereas it would be considered disadvantageous for further research as the distribution of these different learning schemes is not exact but rather random. Students have different learning styles and specific research on the learning styles of each individual is never mentioned. This diversity will be a hindrance to the students' learning as they did not have enough data to comprehend the validity of the specific learning schemes and thus it would not be recommended.

Malipot M. (2020), *Manila Bulletin: DepEd Issues Academic Ease Measures to 'Overwhelmed' Teachers and Students.* According to this article written by a Filipina Journalist residing in the Manila Bulletin news outlet, Malipot M. (2020), the Department of Education implies to improve healthy measures for the Filipino students' mental health. Usec. Diosdado San Antonio explained that these measures were made to help the students adjust into the new ways of learning. The first quarter of the school year was extended for a better adjustment and they disregarded the advancement of learning. This means that they lessened the activities at the self-paced learning to benefit students who are under academic pressure and to those who lack the capability of having the privilege to use enough resources for information. San Antonio added ten highly-recommended measures to field units to ensure flexibility in teaching and learning as a response to the request of teacher and student groups to ease the components of distance learning implementation.

CHALLENGES IN MODULAR AND SELF-PACED LEARNING

Dangle Y. & Sumaoang J. (2020), *The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in the Philippine Secondary Public Schools.* The purpose of this research by Dangle and Sumaoang (2020) is to find out the challenges encountered, opinions, and recommendations of teachers, parents, and students in the implementation of Modular Distance Learning during the School Year 2020-2021. These challenges, opinions and recommendations were identified through a mixed quantitative and qualitative approach by conducting surveys to selected schools. The main challenges that emerged were lack of school funding in the production and delivery of modules; students struggle with self-studying, and parents' lack of knowledge to academically guide their child/children. In conclusion, the study was able to determine the prevailing challenges of the participants in terms of resources, preparedness, and communication.

Sewagegn A. & Diale B. (2019), *Modular/Block teaching: practices and challenges at higher education institutions of Ethiopia.* The purpose of this study conducted by Sewagegn & Diale (2019) was to explore the practices and difficulties of modular teaching in education. Questionnaires and semi-structured interviews were utilized to accumulate information and examined quantitatively (descriptive and inferential statistics) and qualitatively (thematic analysis). Their conclusion was that when using the modular teaching approach, one course is given without the interference of other courses –this helps students to concentrate on one subject at a time. However, the time given does not seem to be sufficient to digest the course efficiently. The system does not emphasise practical skills and theory and practice remain separate, which does not make learning credible.

Olamo T., et al. (2019), *Challenges Hindering the Effective Implementation of the Harmonized Modular Curriculum: The Case of Three Public Universities in Ethiopia.* The purpose of this study conducted by Olamo T., et al. (2019) was to assess the challenges which

hinder the effective implementation of the Harmonized Modular Curriculum. The findings of this study show that the modular curriculum has not been effectively implemented due to some challenges. The challenges include that students are forced to join the Department of English Language and Literature without the basic knowledge, skills, and interest to study, which in its turn makes the teaching-learning process difficult. In conclusion, there are many challenges that were encountered in modular learning/curriculum, like there are challenges regarding courses in the curriculum as time given for block courses is very short to have sufficient practice, assessment and in-depth understanding of the courses' contents. This implies that quality of education is given less emphasis than quantity.

Ramos, M. (2020), *Philippine Daily Inquirer: DepEd Distribution of Modules Remains a Challenge in NCR.* According to Ramos, M. (2020), a Filipina Journalist/Anthropologist, in her written article entitled “DepEd Distribution of Modules Remains a Challenge in NCR” published in the Philippine Daily Inquirer news outlet, as the Department of Education (DepEd) expressed confidence last August 2020 that schools in the Philippines were ready for the class opening on October 5, 2020, the dissemination of self-learning modules was a challenge in Metro Manila. DepEd National Capital Region Director Malcolm Garma stated in a press conference that all of NCR’s 16 school divisions had printed their self-learning modules. However, only three (3) of the sixteen (16) school divisions have achieved 100% distribution rate of the modules. Garma said that a significant number of students, teachers and learners still opted to use printed modules based on their survey, so it will be the default tool for the delivery of learning in NCR until the second quarter of the school year. Garma said, “come third grading period, we will gradually shift to more digital platforms that do not need so much internet connectivity.”

Martinez, M. (2006), *What is Metacognition?* As stated by the author of this study, metacognition serves many diverse functions, as does language. There are three major categories for metacognition: (1) Metamemory and Metacomprehension; (2) Problem Solving; (3) Critical Thinking. Metamemory and Metacomprehension both refer to an understanding of one's own knowledge state. For instances in Metamemory, a student might be asked whether he can name the planets of the solar system in order of their distance from the sun. His answer may contradict to the truth and thus one's awareness is regarded as a cause for one's choice. As for Metacomprehension, independent of learners' true comprehension is whether they realize that their comprehension is good or poor. This also involves awareness in the existing errors such that one might distinguish the right and wrong. Problem solving requires weighing options, exploring subsets of options, and evaluating the results. It involves cognition but so is self-interrogation and lastly, critical thinking is evaluating ideas for the quality of a given subject. It is the judgement of the given subjects whether there exists a sense between them. Automaticity is also a fragment of metacognition as it aids higher order thought. To elaborate, higher and lower thinking do not contradict each other because the working memory is limited in capacity for conscious state and a skilled driver can navigate a familiar route without effort, relying on automated thinking and thus Automaticity is the alteration for conscious state, activating the unconscious state as a result of intelligent cognition. Overall, metacognition is the monitoring and control of thought. Metacognition inside the classroom is important as the metacognitive thought can support persistence and focus.

CHAPTER III

Methodology of the Study

In this chapter, the research methodology used, geographical area where the study was conducted, the design of the study, and the population and sample are described, as well as the instrument used to collect the data, including methods implemented to maintain validity and reliability of the instrument.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

The researchers utilized a Quantitative Research Design. According to Aliaga and Gunderson (2000), quantitative research is a type of research design that explains the phenomena by gathering numerical data that are scrutinized using mathematically based methods, or simply '*equations*'. Furthermore, it ought to answer questions through the use of polls, questionnaires and surveys (Labaree 2009). This method was used to provide a clear and better way of understanding on analyzing the effectiveness of Modular and Self-Paced Learning the selected institution. With this, the researchers used survey questionnaires as a primary data gathering tool.

LOCALE OF THE STUDY

The study shall be conducted in the selected private school, Mary Immaculate Parish Special School. The respondents who are enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality in MIPSS, located in Las Piñas City, shall be surveyed through the internet via Google Forms. The researchers chose Google Forms because it is user-friendly and it would give the researchers the needed information from the students without giving it face-to-face. The study shall be conducted during the academic year 2020-2021.

POPULATION

The target number of respondents are sixty-eight (68) Junior High School students from Mary Immaculate Parish Special School (MIPSS) who are enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality located in Las Piñas City.

GRADE LEVEL	POPULATION	RESPONDENTS
Grade 7	12	6
Grade 8	13	10
Grade 9	10	5
Grade 10	33	29
Total	68	50

Table 1

A total of fifty (50) modular students out of sixty-eight (68) completed the questionnaires between March 7, 2021 and April 12, 2021.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

The research instrument used for collecting information in this study is through conducting a survey with structured questions. The content was implied through extensive research and it involves the efficiency of distance learning to the chosen educational institution. The given questions to be answered are based on published studies and focus on the experiences with regards to self-paced learning.

A survey questionnaire was chosen as a data collection instrument. A questionnaire is a written self-report form designed to gather information that can be obtained through the responses of the subjects. The information obtained through a questionnaire is similar to that obtained by an interview, but the questions tend to have less depth (Burns & Grove 1993).

Data will be collected with the aid of questionnaires to evaluate the students' experiences on being in the Modular Learning Modality in this “new normal.” Questionnaires were decided upon because of the following:

- It ensures a high response rate, as the questionnaires were distributed to respondents via online to complete and were collected automatically by the chosen online platform.
- They require less time and energy to administer.
- It offers the possibility of anonymity because the subjects’ names were not required on the completed questionnaires, only their email addresses were needed to ensure that answers are not duplicated.
- There were lesser chances of becoming biased as they were presented in a consistent manner.
- Most of the items in the questionnaires were closed and were provided with choices, which made it easier to compare the responses.

The conduction of this research involves the use of a structured questionnaire, which was used as a guide for all chosen respondents to answer. All the questions were prepared and planned out thoroughly towards the satisfaction of research objectives.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

In gathering the data, the researchers followed the following procedures:

1. A letter was sent to the Officer-in-charge (OIC) of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School.
2. With the approval of the officer in charge, the researchers distributed the questionnaires to the respondents electronically/online.

3. The researchers collected the questionnaires from the respondents and checked whether all the questions were answered.
4. The data collected were tabulated and processed.

STATISTICAL TREATMENT

The formula below shows the computation for the percentage:

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

- % = Percent
- f = Frequency
- N = Number of respondents

CHAPTER IV

Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

This chapter discusses the data analysis and findings from the questionnaires completed by the Junior High School students who are enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality in Mary Immaculate Parish Special School that were distributed by the researchers. These data are presented in tables following the sequence of the specific research problem.

The purpose of this study was to know if printed modules prepared by the teachers are effective method of delivering the lessons during this time of the pandemic. The objectives of the study were to identify the effectiveness of modules through knowing the advantages, disadvantages, and the challenges that were experienced first-hand by the students while conducting self-paced and modular learning.

Questionnaires were given to the Junior High School Students in Mary Immaculate Parish Special School who are enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality. The survey forms were given through the use of Google Forms to ensure organization and safety. A total of fifty (50) modular students out of sixty-eight (68) completed the questionnaires between March 7, 2021 and April 12, 2021.

The data from the questionnaires were statistically analyzed. The findings are discussed according to sections of the questionnaire. There are five (5) sections of the questionnaire provided by the researchers:

- **Section 1:** Personal Information (Demographics)
- **Section 2:** Advantages of Modular & Self-Paced Learning
- **Section 3:** Disadvantages of Modular & Self-Paced Learning
- **Section 4:** Challenges in Modular & Self-Paced Learning
- **Section 5:** Possible Solutions to ensure Quality Education through Modular & Self-Paced Learning

Personal Information (Demographics)

Grade Level	f	Percentage (%)
Grade 7	6	12%
Grade 8	10	20%
Grade 9	5	10%
Grade 10	29	58%
TOTAL	50	100%

Table 2

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage of the Junior High School students enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality who completed answering the survey questions that were distributed by the researchers. A total of fifty (50) students out of sixty-eight (68) responded. The other eighteen (18) students were not reachable online because of unavoidable circumstances such as no available gadget(s) and/or no internet access. Hence, the reason why they are in the Modular Learning Modality.

Twelve percent (12%) of the respondents were from Grade 7, twenty percent (20%) were from Grade 8, ten percent (10%) were from Grade 9, and fifty-eight percent (58%) of the respondents, which were the largest number, was from Grade 10.

Advantages of Modular and Self-Paced Learning

- 1.) It benefits students who are under academic pressure and lack capability of having the privilege to use enough resources for information.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	4	67%	2	33%
Grade 8	0	0%	0	0%	6	60%	4	40%
Grade 9	2	40%	0	0%	2	40%	1	20%
Grade 10	0	0%	1	3%	19	66%	9	31%

Table 3

The table above (Table 3), shows the Frequency and Percentage of Grade 7 - 10 Students who answered “Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Agree (A) and Strongly Agree (SA)” to the first question in terms of the Advantages of Modular and Self-Paced Learning in Mary Immaculate Parish Special School. 0% of the population from grade 7, 8, and 10 strongly disagree from this statement, as 40% of the grade 9 strongly disagrees. Students from grade 7-9 have a population of 0% that disagrees, while 3% of the grade 10 does. 67% of the grade 7 respondents, 60% from the grade 8, 40% from grade 9, and 66% from the grade 10 students all agree with this. And lastly, 33% from grade 7, 40% of the grade 8 respondents, 20% of the grade 9, and 31% of the grade 10 students all strongly

agree that modular and self-paced learning benefits students under academic pressure and lack resources for information.

2.) Develops student’s accountability, independence and self-reliance.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	1	17%	5	83%
Grade 8	0	0%	0	0%	3	30%	7	70%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	4	80%	1	20%
Grade 10	0	0%	2	7%	11	38%	16	55%

Table 4

Table 4 shows the results from question number two. 0% of the population from grade 7-10 strongly disagree and disagree that modular and self-paced learning develops student’s accountability, independence, and self-reliance. 17% from the grade seven, 30% of the grade 8 students, 80% from the grade 9, and 38% of the grade 10 students all agree. Lastly, 83% grade 7 students, 70% grade 8 students, 20% from the grade 9, and 55% of the grade 10 students strongly agree that modular and self-paced learning develops accountability, independence, and self-reliance.

3.) Encourages Self-learning.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	3	50%	3	50%
Grade 8	2	20%	1	10%	1	10%	6	60%
Grade 9	0	0%	3	60%	2	40%	0	0%
Grade 10	0	0%	2	7%	11	38%	16	55%

Table 5

Table 5 shown above presents 0% of the population from grade 7, 9, and 10 strongly disagrees that modular and self-paced learning encourages self-learning, while only 20% from the grade 8 strongly disagrees. 0% of grade 7 respondents, 10% from the grade 8, 60% of the grade 9, and 7% of grade 10 students disagree with this. 50% of the grade 7 students agree and the other 50% strongly agree. While 10% of the grade 8 students, 40% from grade 9, and 38% of the grade 10 respondents agree, 50% from grade 7, 60% from grade 8, 0% from grade 9, and 55% of the grade 10 strongly agrees that modular and self-paced learning encourages self-learning.

4.) Enhances metacognition.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	1	16.67%	1	16.67%	4	66.66%
Grade 8	0	0%	2	20%	1	10%	7	70%
Grade 9	0	0%	2	40%	3	60%	0	0%
Grade 10	0	0%	1	3%	17	59%	11	38%

Table 6

0% of the population from grades 7 to 10 strongly disagree that modular and self-paced learning enhances metacognition. 16.67% of grade 7 students, 20% from grade 8, 40% from grade 9, and 3% of the grade 10 disagree with this. 16.67% from grade 7, 10% from grade 8, 60% of the grade 9, and 59% of the grade 10 population agree. Lastly, 66.66% of the grade 7, 70% of the grade 8, 0% from grade 9, and 38% from the grade 10 students strongly agree that this enhances metacognition of students.

5.) Increases academic performance of the students.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	4	67%	2	33%
Grade 8	1	10%	0	0%	2	20%	7	70%
Grade 9	1	20%	1	20%	1	20%	2	40%
Grade 10	0	0%	10	34.48%	11	37.93%	8	27.59%

Table 7

As reflected in the table, 0% of the population from grade 7 and 10 strongly disagree, while 10% from the grade 8 and 20% from the grade 9 strongly disagree with

this. 0% of the grade 7 and 8, 20% of the grade 9, and 34.48% from the grade 10 respondents disagree. 67% of the grade 7, 20% of the grade 8, 20% from grade 9, and 37.93% from the grade 10 agree. Lastly, 33% from the grade 7 students, 70% of the grade 8, 40% of the grade 9, and 27.59% of the grade 10 respondents strongly agree that modular and self-paced learning increases academic performance of the students.

6.) Helps monitor students' track for learning.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	1	17%	2	33%	3	50%
Grade 8	1	10%	0	0%	3	30%	6	60%
Grade 9	2	40%	0	0%	3	60%	0	0%
Grade 10	1	3%	4	14%	17	59%	7	24%

Table 8

Delving deeper into the tables, 0% of the population of grade 7 strongly disagree that modular and self-paced learning helps monitor students' track for learning, as 10% from the grade 8, 40% from the grade 9 and 3% from the grade 10. Meanwhile, 17% from grade 7 and 14% from grade 10 disagreed with this. On the other hand, 33% coming from grade 7, 30% from grade 8, 60% from grade 9 and 59% from grade 10 agreed with the statement. Whereas, 50% of grade 7 students together with 60% of the population from grade 8 and 24% from grade 10.

7.) Others

Grade Level	Answers
Grade 7	They have time to focus in order to self-study in any subject(s).
Grade 8	It helps to improve their reading comprehension
Grade 9	
Grade 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modular students have free time for themselves. They do not need to be on their laptop/desktop monitors for the whole day. • Modular students experience less physical side effects such as back pain and eye strains because they only need to study what is on the module. • Allows students to feel more comfortable while studying. • Helps students whether to choose modular or full online in the next school year. • Give students more time to rethink their answers. • I become more responsible as a student, kasi sarili ko lang yung magiging katulong ko para matuto and mas marami akong time para mas maintindihan ko yung every lesson

Table 9

The table indicates the data of the junior high school students from grades 7-10 with regards to their feedback from the use of modular modality. The students stated their opinions on the advantageous category. Under this, the majority of advantageous reasons includes the flexible time given, no exposure from screen radiation, and enhances reading comprehension.

SUMMARY: Advantages Modular and Self-Paced Learning

ADVANTAGES	SD	%	D	%	A	%	SA	%
1. Benefit students who are under academic pressure and lack capability of having the privilege to use enough resources for information.	2	4	1	2	31	62	16	32
2. Develop student’s accountability, independence and self-reliance.	0	0	2	4	19	38	29	58
3. Encourage Self-learning.	2	4	6	12	17	34	25	50
4. Enhance metacognition.	0	0	6	12	22	44	22	44
5. Increase academic performance of the students.	2	4	11	22	18	36	19	38
6. Monitor students' track of learning.	4	8	5	10	25	50	16	32
TOTAL		3%		10%		44%		42%

Table 10

Delving deeper into the table shown above, the majority 62% of the whole population agreed that modular and self-paced learning benefits those who are under academic pressure and lack capability of having the privilege to use enough resources for information and 58% of the students strongly agreed that it develops accountability, their independence and self-reliance. Half percent of the population strongly agreed that it encourages self-learning and monitors their track of learning. Lastly, the 44% of the whole population agreed that it enhances their metacognition and the other 44% strongly agreed with the statement. Overall, majority agreed on the advantages of the modular self-paced learning which records 44%.

Disadvantages of Modular and Self-Paced Learning

1.) Absence of Communication (between the student/s and instructor)

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	3	50%	3	50%
Grade 8	1	10%	4	40%	2	20%	3	30%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	3	60%	2	40%
Grade 10	0	0%	1	3%	15	52%	13	45%

Table 11

The table shown above indicates that 10% of grade 7 students strongly disagree with the absence of communication as a disadvantage of modular and self-paced learning. While 40% of the population from grade 8 and 3% from grade 10 disagreed. However, 50% of grade 7 students, 20% coming from grade 8, 60% from grade 9 and 52% from grade 10 agreed that it is indeed a disadvantage. As 50% of the population from grade 7, 30% from grade 8, 40% from grade 9 as well as 45% from grade 10 strongly agree with the statement.

2.) Errors in modules.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	2	33%	3	50%	1	17%
Grade 8	3	30%	2	20%	3	30%	2	20%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	4	80%	1	20%
Grade 10	2	7%	9	31%	14	48%	4	14%

Table 12

As reflected in the table, 30% of grade 8 and 7% of grade 10 students strongly disagree while 33% from grade 7, 20% from grade 8 and 31% from grade 10 disagree that the errors in modules is not a disadvantage of modular and self-paced learning. Meanwhile, 50% of the population from grade 7, 30% from grade 8, 80% from grade 9 and 48% from grade 10 agreed. However, 17% of grade 7 students with 20% of the population from grades 8 and 9 and 14% from grade 10 strongly agree that it is a disadvantage.

3.) Great number of activities in the module.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	1	16.67%	4	66.66%	1	16.67%
Grade 8	1	10%	1	10%	3	30%	5	50%
Grade 9	2	40%	0	0%	1	20%	2	40%
Grade 10	0	0%	3	10%	10	35%	16	55%

Table 13

Table 13 shows that 10% from grade 8 and 40% from grade 9 strongly disagree while 16.67% from grade 7, 10% from grade 8 and 10% from grade 10 disagree that the great number of activities in the module is not considered as a disadvantage of modular and self-paced learning modules. Whereas, 66.66% of the population from grade 7, 30% from grade 8, 20% from grade 9 and 35% from grade 10 agreed with the statement. As 16.67% from grade 7, 50% from grade 8, 40% from grade 9 and 55% coming from grade 10 strongly agree that it is indeed a disadvantage.

4.) Inadequate individual attention from teachers

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	1	17%	3	50%	2	33%
Grade 8	2	20%	3	30%	4	40%	1	10%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	4	80%	1	20%
Grade 10	1	3%	6	21%	14	48%	8	28%

Table 14

The table above indicated that 20% of grade 8 students as well as 3% of the population coming from grade 10 strongly disagree while 17% from grade 7, 30% from grade 8 and 21% from grade 10 disagreed with the statement stating that the inadequate individual attention from teachers is a disadvantage of modular and self-paced learning. On the other hand, 50% students from grade 7, 40% coming from grade 8, 80% from grade 9 and 48% of the population from grade 10 agreed together with 33% from grade 7, 10% from grade 8, 20% from grade 9 and 28% from grade 10 who strongly agreed that it is a disadvantage.

5.) Invites (or is considered) fun rather than learning

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	1	16.67%	4	66.66%	1	16.67%
Grade 8	1	10%	3	30%	2	20%	4	40%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	2	40%	3	60%
Grade 10	4	13.79%	4	13.79%	17	58.63%	4	13.79%

Table 15

As reflected in Table 15, none of the population in grade 7 strongly disagree that modular learning invites fun rather than learning but the 16.67% strongly agreed. Meanwhile, the other 16.67% disagreed, but the majority 66.66% agreed. For the grade 8 students, only 10% of them strongly disagreed, but the 40% strongly agreed. on the other hand, 30% disagreed, while the remaining 20% agreed. Regarding the grade 9 students, none of them disagreed nor strongly disagreed because the whole population agreed, except the majority 60% strongly agreed. Lastly, the grade 10 students tied up having 13.79% people disagreeing and strongly disagreeing. However, the other 13.79% strongly agreed but the majority 58.63% plainly agreed.

6.) Negative effect on physical and mental health (e.g. lack of sleep, focus, distraction, anxiety, etc.)

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	1	16.67%	1	16.67%	3	50%	1	16.67%
Grade 8	3	30%	1	10%	2	20%	4	40%
Grade 9	0	0%	1	20%	2	40%	2	40%
Grade 10	1	3%	8	28%	6	21%	14	48%

Table 16

The illustrative graph above shows that 16.67% in grade 7 disagree and strongly disagreed about having a negative effect on physical and mental health while the other 16.67% strongly agreed. 50% of the grade 7 population agreed. As for the grade 8, 10% of them disagree, while 30% strongly disagree. On the other hand, 20% agreed, while the majority 40% strongly agreed. For the grade 9 students, none of them strongly disagreed but 20% disagreed. On the flip side, 40% of them agreed, and the other 40% strongly agreed. Lastly, with the grade 10 population, only 3% strongly disagreed, but 28% disagreed. The 21% plainly agreed and equally important, the majority 48% strongly agreed with the statement.

7.) Less opportunity for the students to achieve full potential.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	1	16.67%	4	66.66%	1	16.67%
Grade 8	2	20%	5	50%	2	20%	1	10%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	2	40%	3	60%
Grade 10	2	7%	6	21%	10	34%	11	38%

Table 17

As observed in table 17, in modular learning, none of the grade 7 students strongly disagreed about having less opportunity for the students to achieve full potential and only 16.67% disagree, because the majority 66.66% agreed while the remaining 16.67% strongly agreed. for the grade 8 students, the 20% strongly disagreed, while the majority 50% disagreed. On the contrary, the other 20% agreed, while the remaining 10% strongly agreed. In terms of the grade 9 students, none of them disagreed, nor strongly disagreed, because the 40% plainly agreed while the majority 60% strongly agreed. Last but not the least, 7% of the grade 10 students strongly disagreed, and the other 21% plainly disagreed. Contrarily, the 34% agreed, and 38% of them strongly agreed with the statement.

8.) Others

Grade Level	Answers
Grade 7	Disadvantages is that we'll not able to have learn from the teacher
Grade 8	Lack of Interaction from other students
Grade 9	
Grade 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Late passing of grade (card)• Students can't really learn the topics in the modules• The only disadvantage that I encounter is the time management, nahihirapan po ako pagsabay sabayin lahat ng kailangan gawin

Table 18

The table indicates the data of the junior high school students from grades 7-10 in regards to their feedback from the use of modular modality. The students stated their opinions on the disadvantageous category. Under this, the majority of disadvantageous reasons include difficulty in comprehending the topics given in the modules, inconsistent communication, and the numerous tasks with time constraint.

SUMMARY: Disadvantages Modular and Self-Paced Learning

DISADVANTAGES	SD	%	D	%	A	%	SA	%
1. Absence of Communication (between the student/s and instructor)	1	2	5	10	23	46	21	42
2. Errors in modules.	5	10	13	26	24	48	8	16
3. Great number of activities in the module.	3	6	5	10	18	36	24	48
4. Inadequate individual attention from teachers	3	6	10	20	25	50	12	24
5. Invites (or is considered) fun rather than learning	5	10	8	16	25	50	12	24
6. Negative effect on physical and mental health (e.g. lack of sleep, focus, distraction, anxiety, etc.)	5	10	11	22	13	26	21	42
7. Less opportunity for the students to achieve full potential.	4	8	12	24	18	36	16	32
TOTAL		7%		18%		42%		33%

Table 19

To summarize the table shown above, half of the population agreed that modular learning invites fun rather than learning and gives inadequate individual attention from the teachers. The 48% of the students agreed that there are errors in the modules given and 46% agreed that there is absence of communication. 42% of the population strongly agreed that modular learning has negative effect on physical and mental health while 36% agreed that there is less opportunity for the students to achieve full potential. Overall, majority agreed on the disadvantages of modular self-paced learning which records 42%.

Challenges in Modular & Self-Paced Learning

1.) Needs improvement in reading, pronunciation, and comprehension.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	3	50%	3	50%
Grade 8	1	10%	2	20%	2	20%	5	50%
Grade 9	0	0%	2	40%	3	60%	0	0%
Grade 10	4	14%	5	17%	15	52%	5	17%

Table 20

As shown in the table above regarding the respondents' thoughts about having the needs to improve in reading, pronunciation, and comprehension, none of the grade 7 agreed, nor disagreed because half of the population agreed while the other half strongly agreed. As for the grade 8 students, only 10% strongly disagreed, while the 20% disagreed. Meanwhile, the other 20% agreed and half of the population strongly agreed. Next are the grade 9 students with 0% strongly disagreeing, but 40% disagreeing. On the other hand, the majority 60% agreed, although none of them strongly agreed. Lastly, the 14 % of grade 10 students strongly disagreed, while the 17% disagreed. On the contrary, the other 17% strongly agreed, and the majority 52% plainly agreed with the statement.

2.) Parents' lack of knowledge to academically assist their child/children.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	1	16.67%	1	16.67%	3	50%	1	16.67%
Grade 8	0	0%	4	40%	2	20%	4	40%
Grade 9	0	0%	1	20%	3	60%	1	20%
Grade 10	4	14%	10	34%	8	28%	7	24%

Table 21

Referring to the table 21 shown above, the grade 7 students tied up having 16.67% disagreeing and strongly disagreeing with parents' lacking of knowledge to academically assisting their child/children. On the other hand, half of the population agreed, while the other 16.67% strongly agreed. Next, none of the grade 8 students strongly disagreed, but the 40% disagreed. Meanwhile, the other 40% strongly agreed, and the 20% plainly agreed. As for the grade 9 students, none of them strongly disagree but 20% disagreed. The sums up having the majority 60% agreeing while the other 20% strongly agreeing. Last but not the least, 14% of the grade 10 students strongly agreed, while 34% plainly disagreed. However, 29% of them agreed and 24% strongly agreed with the statement.

3.) Setting and following study time.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	1	17%	2	33%	3	50%
Grade 8	0	0%	1	10%	2	20%	7	70%
Grade 9	0	0%	2	40%	2	40%	1	20%
Grade 10	2	7%	1	3%	11	38%	15	52%

Table 22

Shown above is the results of table 22. It presents the Frequency and Percentage of grade 7 - 10 Students to the third question which is setting and following study time, in terms of the Challenges of Modular and Self-Paced Learning. 0% of the population from grade 7,8 and 9 strongly disagrees from this statement, while only 7% from grade 10 strongly disagrees. 17% of the grade 7 respondents, 10% from the grade 8, 40% from grade 9, and 3% from the grade 10 students disagree with this. 33% of the grade 7 respondents, 20% from grade 8, 40% from grade 9, and 38% from the grade 10 students agree with this statement. And lastly, 50% from grade 7, 70% from grade 8, 20% from grade 9, and 52% from grade 10 students all strongly agree to this statement.

4.) Passive attitude towards learning

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	4	67%	2	33%
Grade 8	0	0%	2	20%	3	30%	6	60%
Grade 9	2	40%	0	0%	3	60%	0	0%
Grade 10	1	3%	6	21%	14	48%	8	28%

Table 23

Table 23 indicates the result from question number 4 which is passive attitude towards learning, in terms of the Challenges in Modular and Self-Paced Learning. 0% of the population from grade 7 and 8, 40% from grade 9, and 3% from grade 10 strongly disagree with the statement. 0% of the respondents from grade 7 and 9, 20% from grade 8, and 21% from grade 10 disagree with this statement. 67% of the respondents from grade 7, 30% from grade 8, 60% from grade 9 and 48% from grade 10 agree with this statement. And lastly, 33% from grade 7, 60% from grade 8, 0% from grade 9, and 28% from grade 10 respondents strongly agree with this statement.

5.) Time given for courses (subjects) is very short to have sufficient practice, assessment and in-depth understanding of the courses' contents.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	4	67%	2	33%
Grade 8	0	0%	2	20%	2	20%	6	60%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	3	60%	2	40%
Grade 10	1	3%	8	28%	15	52%	5	17%

Table 24

Table 24 presents the result from question number 5 which is Time given for courses (subjects) is very short to have sufficient practice, assessment and in-depth understanding of the courses' contents, in terms of the Challenges in Modular and Self-Paced Learning. 0% of the population from grade 7,8, and 9 strongly disagree with this statement, while only 3% from grade 10 strongly disagree. 0% of the respondents from grade 7 and 9, 20% from grade 8, and 28% from grade 10 disagree with this statement. 67% of the respondents from grade 7, 20% from grade 8, 60% from grade 9, and 52% from grade 10 agree with this statement. And lastly, 33% from grade 7, 60% from grade 8, 40% from grade 9, and 17% from grade 10 respondents strongly agree with this statement.

6.) Others

Grade Level	Answers
Grade 7	Finishing on time
Grade 8	
Grade 9	
Grade 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Quizzes • Trying to learn the lesson by yourself • Pag nagkasabay sabay ng deadline

Table 25

The table indicates the data of the junior high school students from grades 7-10 in regards to their feedback from the use of modular modality. The students stated their opinions on the challenges category. Under this, the majority reasons the existence of online quizzes, isolation, and restricted time given the load of tasks as challenges in the use of modular modality.

SUMMARY: Challenges in Modular and Self-Paced Learning

CHALLENGES	SD	%	D	%	A	%	SA	%
1. Needs improvement in reading, pronunciation, and comprehension.	5	10	9	18	23	46	13	26
2. Parents' lack of knowledge to academically assist their child/children.	5	10	16	32	16	32	13	26
3. Setting and following study time.	2	4	5	10	17	34	26	52
4. Passive attitude towards learning	3	6	8	16	22	44	17	34
5. Time given for courses (subjects) is very short to have sufficient practice, assessment and in-depth understanding of the courses' contents.	1	2	10	20	24	48	15	30
TOTAL		6%		19%		41%		34%

Table 26

As observed in the table shown above, it indicates the challenges met by students and 46% agreed that they need improvement in reading, pronunciation, and

comprehension. The results tied up having 32% of the students agreeing and 32% disagreeing about parents' lacking of knowledge to academically assist their child/children. More than half of the population with 52% strongly agreed that the setting and following of study time and 44% agreed having passive attitude towards leaning is considered a challenge. And lastly, 48% strongly agreed that the Time given for courses (subjects) is very short to have sufficient practice, assessment and in-depth understanding of the courses' contents.

Possible Solutions to Ensure Quality Learning

- 1.) Modules must be validated for the quality assurance and progress must be monitored.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	3	50%	3	50%
Grade 8	1	10%	0	0%	3	30%	6	60%
Grade 9	1	20%	0	0%	3	60%	1	20%
Grade 10	3	10.34%	3	10.34%	11	38%	12	41.38%

Table 27

As observed in the results from question number 1 which is modules must be validated for the quality assurance and progress must be monitored, in terms of the Possible Solutions to Ensure Quality. 0% of the population from grade 7, 10% from grade 8, 20% from grade 9, and 10.34% from grade 10 strongly disagree with this statement. 0% of the respondents from grade 7,8 and 9 disagree with this statement, while only 10.34% from grade 10 disagree. 50% of the respondents from grade 7, 30% from grade 8, 60% from

grade 9, and 38% from grade 10 agree with this statement. And lastly, 50% from grade 7, 60% from grade 8, 20% from grade 9, and 41.38% from grade 10 respondents strongly agree with this statement

2.) The topics must be simplified, and teachers must give more examples.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	1	17%	3	50%	2	33%
Grade 8	0	0%	0	0%	2	20%	8	80%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	2	40%	3	60%
Grade 10	0	0%	0	0%	8	28%	21	72%

Table 28

The interpretation of table number 28 in question number 2 which is the topic must be simplified, and teachers must give more examples, in terms of Possible Solutions and Quality, reveals that 0% of the population from grade 7,8,9 and 10 strongly disagree with this statement. 17% of the respondents from grade 7 and 0% from grade 8,9 and 10 disagree with this statement. 50% of the respondents from grade 7, 20% from grade 8, 40% from grade 9, and 28% from grade 10 agree with this statement. And lastly, 33% from grade 7, 80% from grade 8, 60% from grade 9, and 72% from grade 10 respondents strongly agree with this statement.

3.) Follow ups from teachers are highly encouraged.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	4	67%	2	33%
Grade 8	0	0%	0	0%	3	30%	7	70%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	2	40%	3	60%
Grade 10	0	0%	1	3%	13	45%	15	52%

Table 29

The table above presents that 0% of the population from grade 7, 8, 9, and 10 Strongly disagree that follow ups from teachers is not a possible solution to ensure quality education of modular and self-paced learning modules. Students from Grade 7-9 have a population of 0% that disagree while 3% of the Grade 10 does. 67% of the grade 7 respondents, 30% from the grade 8, 40% from the grade 9, 45% from the grade 10 students that all agree with this. And lastly 33% from grade 7, and 70% from grade 8, and 60% from grade 9, and 52% from grade 10 strongly agree that it is indeed one of the possible solutions.

4.) Evaluation of modules.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	3	50%	3	50%
Grade 8	0	0%	0	0%	6	60%	4	40%
Grade 9	0	0%	1	20%	2	40%	2	40%
Grade 10	0	0%	0	0%	17	59%	12	41%

Table 30

Delving deeper into the tables, 0% of the population from the grade 7-10 strongly disagree from this statement. Students from Grade 7, 8, 10 have a population of 0% that disagree while 20% of the grade 9 does. 50% of the grade 7 respondents, 60% from grade 8, 40% from the grade 9, 59% from the grade 10 students that all agree with this. And lastly 50% from grade 7, 40% from grade 8, and grade 9, and 41% from grade 10 students who strongly agree that evaluation of modules is one of the possible solutions.

5.) Give appropriate praises, encouragement, and rewards to heighten their child's motivation to learn.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	3	50%	3	50%
Grade 8	0	0%	1	10%	2	20%	7	70%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	2	40%	3	60%
Grade 10	0	0%	2	7%	11	38%	16	55%

Table 31

As reflected in the table above, 0% of the population from grade 7, 8, 9, and 10 strongly disagree from this statement. Students from grade 7 and 9 have a population of 0% that disagree, while grade 8 is 10% and grade 10 is 7% does. 50% from grade 7, 20% from grade 8, 40% from grade 9 and 38% from grade 10 students that all agree with this. And lastly 50% from grade 7, 70% from grade 8, and 60% from grade 9 and 55% from grade 10 students who strongly agree that giving appropriate praises, encouragement, and rewards to heighten their child's motivation to learn is one of the possible solutions for ensuring quality education of modular and self-paced learning modules.

6.) Prepare a conducive learning study space for the learner

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	2	33%	4	67%
Grade 8	0	0%	0	0%	5	50%	5	50%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	3	60%	2	40%
Grade 10	0	0%	1	3%	13	45%	15	52%

Table 32

The table revealed that 0% of the population from 7-10 strongly disagree with preparing a conducive learning study space for the learner is not a possible solution for ensuring quality education. Students from grade 7-9 have a population of 0% that disagree, while 3% of the grade 10 does. 33% of the grade 7 respondents, 50% from the grade 8, 60% from grade 9, and 45% from grade 10 students all agree with this. And lastly 67% from grade 7, 50% from grade 8, 40% from grade 9, and 52% from grade 10 students who strongly agree with the statement.

7.) Parents should regularly check their child’s workweek plan and make sure that the learner sticks to their schedule.

Grade Level	Strongly Disagree (SD)		Disagree (D)		Agree (A)		Strongly Agree (SA)	
	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
Grade 7	0	0%	0	0%	4	67%	2	33%
Grade 8	0	0%	2	20%	3	30%	5	50%
Grade 9	0	0%	0	0%	4	80%	1	20%
Grade 10	0	0%	1	3%	8	28%	20	69%

Table 33

The table above shows that 0% of the population from grade 7-10 strongly disagree from this statement. Students from 7 and 9 have a population of 0% while 20% from grade 8 and 3% from grade 10 disagreed. Meanwhile, 67% of the grade 7 respondents, 30% from grade 8, 80% from grade 9 and 28% from grade 10 students that all agree with this. And lastly, 33% from grade 7, 50% from grade 8, 20% from grade 9 and 69 % from grade 10 students strongly agree that parents should regularly check their child’s workweek plan and make sure that the learner sticks to their schedule.

8.) Others	
Grade level	Answers
Grade 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parents assists students in answering module
Grade 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More time/days of answering the modules • Parent should guide them on their modules • Parents help the child to answer the module • Parents should guide their child in the online class if the learner is having trouble in their computer or laptop • Less activities and task • The internet connection
Grade 9	
Grade 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers should not give hard tasks to the students • Motivate them to learn • Teachers should not ignore their students' messages since we are waiting for their response. Students are even willing to wait no matter how long just for our questions and concerns to be answered. • Lessons should be on the printed modules. • Fair modules from online • Students must be honest and fair. Honesty is an important trait to have in your academic and professional life. • Self-control • Try meeting the students every once a week • Modular students must be prioritize, especially pagdating sa modules and activity for us to have an extra points

Table 34

The table indicates the data of the junior high school students from Grades 7-10 in regards to their feedback from the use of modular modality. The students stated their opinions on the solutions category. Under this, the majority suggests the guidance of parents, reduction of activities, adequate attention from teachers as well as interaction, and the extension of time in regards to deadlines.

SUMMARY: POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS TO ENSURE QUALITY LEARNING

POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS	SD	%	D	%	A	%	SA	%
1. Modules must be validated for the quality assurance and progress must be monitored.	5	10	3	6	20	40	22	44
2. The topics must be simplified, and teachers must give more examples.	0	0	1	2	15	30	34	68
3. Follow ups from teachers are highly encouraged.	0	0	1	2	22	44	27	54
4. Evaluation of modules.	0	0	1	2	28	56	21	42
5. Give appropriate praises, encouragement, and rewards to heighten their child's motivation to learn.	0	0	3	6	18	36	29	58
6. Prepare a conducive learning study space for the learner	0	0	1	2	23	46	26	52
TOTAL		2%		3%		42%		53%

Table 35

As reflected in the table, the majority 68% of the students strongly agreed that the topics must be simplified, and teachers must give more examples. The 58% of the students strongly agreed about giving appropriate praises, encouragement, and rewards to heighten their child's motivation to learn and 54% of them, strongly agreed that follow ups from teachers are highly encouraged. 56% of the population agreed with the idea of evaluating the modules, and 46% agreed about preparing a conducive learning study space for the learner. Overall, majority strongly agree with the possible solutions stated which records 53%.

CHAPTER V

Summary, Conclusions, and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of the findings, conclusions, and the recommendations based on the data analyzed in the previous chapter. The Effectiveness of the Modular and Self-Paced Learning of the Junior High School students from Mary Immaculate Parish Special School was researched by determining the advantages, disadvantages, and challenges encountered by the specific group of students.

SUMMARY

The focus of this study was to determine the Effectiveness of Modular and Self-Paced Learning in Mary Immaculate Parish Special School. The background of this study was done by studying the literature on the situation. The background of the research problem covers the advantages, disadvantages, and the challenges met by the students enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality. It also aims to know and to discuss the possible solutions to ensure quality education in the Modular Learning Modality in Mary Immaculate Parish Special School. Its impact on the students' personal lives and the success rate of measures implemented by the school to conduct a successful modular and self-paced approach to learning was discussed and was shown in chapter four.

The literature study was done in chapter two on the recent articles and researches that were already conducted with regards to modular and self-paced approach to learning especially in these times of the COVID-19 Pandemic. The suggestions by reliable authors and researchers, which was discussed in their research papers, and strategies on helping the

students learn better and to acquire more knowledge using the modular learning approach regardless of going through a global pandemic or not, were discussed.

The objectives of this study were to:

- Evaluate whether the Modular Learning Modality in Mary Immaculate Parish Special School is successful on the first year of implementation or not.
- Determine if the Modular Learning Modality does not leave those students who lack resources behind.
- Explore and to know the experiences of the students enrolled in the Modular Learning Modality.
- Identify if there are any other factors which are being experienced by the students.
- Make recommendations to improve the Modular Learning Modality in Mary Immaculate Parish Special School.
- Make recommendations and give suggestions for further research in this field.

FINDINGS

The finding of the study based on the results shown in the previous chapter are discussed in this section.

1. What are the advantages of self-paced learning?

The top three answers with regards to the advantages of modular and self-paced learning are the following:

1. Benefits students who are under academic pressure and lack capability of having the privilege to use enough resources for information.
2. Develops student's accountability, independence and self-reliance.
3. Encourages Self-learning, and monitors student's track of learning.

The majority, sixty percent (60%), agree that modular and self-paced learning benefits students who are under academic pressure and lack enough resources for information. 58% of the population strongly agree that self-paced learning develops student's accountability, independence and self-reliance. 50% of the junior high school students enrolled in the modular learning modality strongly agree that modular and self-paced learning encourages self-learning. Also, 50% of the respondents agree that this learning modality monitors students' track of learning. Other answers provided by the students include that they have less screen time from computers. They also experience less negative physical effects such as back pain and eye strains.

2. *What are the disadvantages of self-paced learning?*

In terms of the disadvantages of modular and self-paced learning, the top three answers are of the following:

1. Inadequate individual attention from teachers and Invites (or is considered) fun rather than learning.
2. Errors in modules and Great number of activities in the module.
3. Absence of Communication (between the student/s and instructor).

The majority fifty percent (50%) agree that modular and self-paced learning inadequate individual attention from teachers and invites (or is considered) fun rather than learning. 48% of the respondents strongly agree that modular learning has a great number of activities in the module. Also, 48% of the students agree that there are errors in modules. 46% of the population agree that this learning modality has an absence of communication (between the student/s and instructor).

3. What challenges were met by the students conducting self-paced learning?

The findings with regards to the challenges met by the students, the following show the top three answers:

1. Setting and following study time.
2. Time given for courses (subjects) is very short to have sufficient practice.
3. Needs improvement in reading, pronunciation, and comprehension.

52% of the population from the junior high school students strongly agree that setting and following the study time is one of the challenges they met during modular and self-paced learning. 48% of students who are currently enrolled in the modular learning modality agreed with the statement, stating that the time given for courses (subjects) is very short to have sufficient practice. Majority forty-six (46%) agree with the statement regarding the need for improvement in reading, pronunciation and comprehension. Other answers include finishing on time, online quizzes, isolation and restricted time given the load of tasks as challenges in the use of modular modality.

4. *What are the possible solutions to ensure quality education to students given the challenges?*

The top three answers from what the students think that the possible solutions to implement in order for the modular learning approach to be improved are the following:

1. The topics must be simplified, and teachers must give more examples.
2. Give appropriate praises, encouragement, and rewards to heighten their child's motivation to learn.
3. Evaluation of modules.

68% of the respondents from junior high school strongly agree that the topics must be simplified, and teachers must give more examples. 58% of the population strongly agree that this learning modality should give appropriate praises, encouragement, and rewards to heighten their child's motivation to learn. 56% of junior high school students agree that there should be an evaluation of modules.

From the researchers' hypothesis that the advantages, disadvantages, and challenges have an impact on the effectiveness of self-paced learning through the modules, and their assumption that the self-paced learning of the Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Special School is effective, the findings show that the solutions category holds the greatest quantitative data as it contains 68% of students who strongly agree that teachers must give more examples as well as topics that must be simplified. The advantages section holds the greatest quantitative data between the challenges and disadvantages as it contains 60% in regards to the existing benefits for the unprivileged students of those who lack enough resources such as technology. The disadvantages section holds the majority of 50%

of respondents in regards to inadequate individual attention from teachers as well as students considering the modules as fun rather than learning. Lastly, the challenges section holds the majority of 52% of respondents in regards to the setting and the given time constraint.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results from the previous chapter and the findings, the researchers therefore conclude the following:

- 1.) The Modular and Self-Paced Learning is advantageous for students, especially to those who are pressured academically to keep up with others and to those who do not have enough resources to conduct online learning such as laptops, phones, desktops, and a stable internet connection. It is also advantageous in a way that it helps the students practice self-discipline and self-reliance, as they do not have fixed schedules just like those who are fully online. It also helps encourage self-learning, which may enhance their metacognitive skills and strategies. It is also an advantage in a way that it monitors the student's progress in learning because the teachers manually check their modules. Modular and Self-Paced Learning in MIPSS is also advantageous because they experience less negative physical side effects such as back pain and eye strains from sitting in front of the computer for long periods of time.
- 2.) Modular and Self-paced learning is disadvantageous for students in a way that they encounter errors in modules and a great number of activities in the module. Another disadvantage is that because it has inadequate individual attention from teachers,

and invites (or is considered) fun rather than learning. Another disadvantage that the students encountered, is that it causes absence of communication (between the student/s and instructor). Students cannot really understand the topics that are in the modules and they need the help/guide of their teachers. And lastly, it is disadvantageous because they will not be able to learn straight from the teacher and will have less interaction from them and other fellow students.

- 3.) Setting and following study time is one of the problems that students experience during modular and self-paced learning. Another challenge that students pointed out is the inadequate amount of time given for courses (subjects) to have sufficient practice, especially when tasks are given simultaneously and have the same deadlines. Students also have a hard time learning by themselves as some of them lack reading, pronunciation and comprehension.
- 4.) In terms of the possible solutions to ensure quality education, Modular and Self-Paced Learning should increase illustrations as examples to enable understanding for students who have difficulties in grasping questions in mock tests. Another solution would be improving a child's motivation by giving encouragement, rewards, and appropriate praises to furthermore enhance their growth and motivation towards learning. The evaluation of modules can improve the quality of learning as the evaluation consists of whether there are grammatical errors, enough data, and quality standards to furnish excellence.
- 5.) With regards to the researchers' hypothesis, the advantages section holds the greatest quantitative data between the challenges and disadvantages. Despite the

hindrance in accommodation of learning, the existing advantages outweigh the negative circumstances in self-paced learning. The solutions category holds the greatest quantitative data, giving emphasis on what needs to be improved and thus the self-paced learning fails to reach the quality standards of excellence. However, this feedback will be a valid reason to enhance the reliability and validity of modules. The existing solutions will increase the advantages of self-paced learning, recommending modular modality for the unprivileged as further evaluations in the future.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are offered in order to improve and ensure the quality of modules as well as to solve problems discussed in the study.

Learners

- 1.) Students should practice their time and priority management skills.
- 2.) Students must keep away/remove distractions such as television and things that will cause them to lose their focus.
- 3.) The researchers recommend students to have a separate space intended for studying only for them to focus and have less distractions while studying and answering their modules.
- 4.) Students should make an effort to read a book or re-read their modules during their free time and check for the pronunciation of unfamiliar words they encounter. With this, students are not only able to improve their reading and pronunciation skills but their comprehension as well.

Teachers

- 1.) The content of the modules given to the students must be relevant or packed with important information only and presented with more examples.
- 2.) The pictures and examples in the modules given should be clear to avoid confusion and to not give the students a hard time understanding an item.
- 3.) Teachers must reach out more to the students via messenger or even communicate through text messages.
- 4.) Enhance their students' metacognition through giving reflective exercises regarding the ambitions they have in life and giving little notes.
- 5.) Teachers should use the Metacognitive Assignment Revision Tool in giving homework. This tool is designed to help instructors incorporate metacognition in existing assignments.
- 6.) Giving them review tips and advice in regards to reviewing exams and answering mock tests.
- 7.) Designing the content of modules in an organized manner may be recommended to enhance the student's imagination and increase motivation.
- 8.) The teachers must limit the given activities in the module. If this is not possible, the school should at least give an ample amount of time for the students to finish their modules.
- 9.) The modules that will be distributed to the students shall include motivations that will inspire them to do and finish their modules.

Parents

- 1.) Parents and/or guardians should guide the students with their studies but give them freedom on how they will manage their time for academic and other personal activities as long as they balance it ideally.
- 2.) Parents are advised to pay more attention with their children's tasks and guide them with their studies to avoid unnecessary distractions while doing their modules.

School Administration

- 1.) The School Administration, specifically the Academic Coordinator(s) and teachers should check the modules for errors before distributing them to the students to avoid confusion.

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APPENDICES

Permission Letter

March 3, 2021

Ma'am Soledad Cabinte
MIPSS Institutional OIC
Avocado Drive, Agro Homes 1
Moonwalk Village, Talon 5
Las Pinas, Metro Manila

Dear Ma'am Sol:

Greetings!

As representative of our group under ICT Strand, who presently working on our research entitled, "*The Effectiveness of Self-Paced Learning to the Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School*", would like to ask for permission to conduct a survey to the Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School, specifically those who are under self-paced/modular learning, as respondents for our research.

Rest assured that the said information will be used for academic purposes only and not for any other reasons or for personal gain.

I, together with my groupmates Pauleen Ann N. Dingcong, Allysson O. Tumangday, Kirsten Ashley M. Magpantay, Ramelle John M. Trasporto, and John Loyd A. Carnasa, we thank you very much for considering this request.

Sincerely,

Juliana Lynelle B. Tribunal
12 ICT – St. Benedict
Research Group Leader

Mary Immaculate Parish Special School

(Recognized By DepEd, Member : DOPPSA, MAPSA, CEAP, FAPE-PEAC Accredited)

March 3, 2021

Ms. Riyo V. Dava
MIPSS Registrar
Avocado Drive, Agro Homes 1
Moonwalk Village, Talon 5
Las Pinas, Metro Manila

To Ms. Riyo Dava;

I, Juliana Lynelle B. Tribunal, am a Grade 12 student of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School (MIPSS) ICT Strand. I represent our group.

I am writing this letter to request from your good office the population of Junior High School Students, who are in the Modular Learning Modality, as respondents for our research entitled, *“The Effectiveness of Self-Paced Learning to the Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School”*. This is in the partial fulfillment of the requirement in Inquiries, Investigations, & Immersion for Grade 12. I humbly ask that you would send the exact population and list of names of students from the modular learning modality, so that our group would have accurate data and that we would know who are the students we should reach out.

Rest assured that the said information will be used for academic purposes only and not for any other reasons or for personal gain.

I, together with my groupmates Pauleen Ann N. Dingcong, Allysson O. Tumangday, Kirsten Ashley M. Magpantay, Ramelle John M. Trasporto, and John Loyd A. Carnasa, we thank you very much for considering this request.

Sincerely,

Noted by:

Juliana Lynelle B. Tribunal
12 ICT – St. Benedict
Research Group Leader

Dr. Anthony P. Venus
Instructor for Grade 12 Inquiries,
Investigations, and
Immersion

Research Instrument

February 25, 2021

Greetings!

We, the Grade 12 St. Benedict are presently conducting a study entitled: "The Effectiveness of Self-Paced Learning of the Junior High School Students of Mary Immaculate Parish Special School," in partial fulfilment of the requirements in Inquiries, Investigation and Immersion.

Rest assured that your identity will remain confidential and the answers will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank You and God bless!

Sincerely,
The Researchers

NAME: (OPTIONAL) _____

Grade level:

Grade 7 Grade 8 Grade 10

Direction: Please put a check mark (/) on the scale which corresponds to your answer.

- 1- Strongly Disagree (SD)
2- Disagree (D)
3- Agree (A)
4 - Strongly Agree (SA)

I. ADVANTAGES OF SELF-PACED LEARNING

Table with 5 columns (Statement, SD, D, A, SA) and 6 rows of advantages of self-paced learning.

II. DISADVANTAGES OF SELF-PACED LEARNING

	SD	D	A	SA
1. Absence of communication				
2. Errors in modules				
3. Great number of activities in the module				
4. Inadequate individual attention from teachers				
5. Invite fun than learning				
6. Negative effect on Physical and mental health (Lack of sleep, focus, distraction, anxiety etc)				
7. Less opportunity for the students to achieve full potential				
Others: (Please specify other disadvantages not included in the list)				

III. CHALLENGES OF SELF-PACED LEARNING

	SD (1)	D (2)	A (3)	SA (4)
1. Need improvement in reading, pronunciation, and comprehension.				
2. Parents' lack of knowledge to academically assist their child/children				
3. Setting and following study time				
4. Passive attitude towards learning				
5. Sufficient practice, assessment and in-depth understanding of the courses' contents				
Others: (Please specify other challenges not included in the list)				

IV. POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS TO ENSURE QUALITY EDUCATION THROUGH SELF-PACED LEARNING

	SD	D	A	SA
1. Modules must be validated for the quality assurance and progress must be monitored.				
2. The topics must be simplified, and teachers must give more examples				
3. Follow ups from teachers are highly encouraged				
4. Evaluation of modules				
5. Give appropriate praises, encouragement, and rewards to heighten their child's motivation to learn.				
6. Prepare a conducive learning study space for the learner				
7. Parents should regularly check their child's workweek plan and make sure that the learner sticks to their schedule.				
Others: (Please specify other possible solutions not included in the list)				